

GRAMMATICAL PROBLEMS OF RENDERING POLITICAL TEXTS FROM ENGLISH INTO UZBEK

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The translation process of political literature from one language into another is inevitable without necessary grammatical transformations (change of structure). It gets great importance while making translation to add or omit some words since the structures of languages are quite different.

Grammatical transformations are characterized by various principles – grammatical, and lexical as well, though the principal role is given to grammatical ones. Very often these grammatical changes are mixed so that they have lexical-grammatical character.

*The **vigil** of the British Embassy, **supported** last week by many prominent people and still continuing, the marches last Saturday, the resolutions or organizations **have done something to show** that Blair doesn't speak for Britain.*

*O'tgan hafta ko'plab taniqli odamlar tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlangan va hali ham davom etayotgan Britaniya elchixonasining **hushyorligi**, o'tgan shanba kungi yurishlar, rezolyutsiyalar yoki tashkilotlar Bler Britaniya nomidan gapirmasligini **ko'rsatish uchun nimadir qildi**.*

While translating this article we have made the following changes.

The sentence was divided into two parts. We often do that when translating short newspaper articles (news in brief) and the first lines of the articles of informative character (leads). Practically, we are forced to do that because the first lines usually contain main information given in the paragraph. These sentences containing various information are not characteristic to the style of

Uzbek writing. The division of the sentence made us repeat the word *демонстрация*.

The word *vigil – hushyorlik* acquired here quite another political meaning *sutka davomidagi namoyish*. Since *tungi hushyorlik* is one of the semantic components of the word *vigil* the term *sutka davomidagi namoyish* fully renders the sense of the given word. Besides, we have to mention that one of the words was translated like word expression *ko`mak olgan*.

We have also added additional words like *у здания (посольства), состоявшиеся (в субботу походы), а также принятые различными (организациями резолюции)*. The word *last* in the *last Saturday* was omitted because it would make the translation more difficult, but we can conceive it by the contextual meaning of the sentence.

The strengthening function of the phrase *have done something to show* was rendered by the adverb *aniq guvohlik beradi*.

And the English cliché *to speak for* was translated by the Uzbek one *nomidan gapirmoq*. And at last I should say that I metonymically translated the word *Britain* into *butun ingliz xalqi*.

Thus, while translating this sentence we have made use of grammatical transformations and lexical as well.

The structural features of English language require structural completeness of the sentence. One can not omit a word without supplying another one instead. This criterion is governed by stylistic preference of the language to prevent word and make the sentence more emphatic.

Even if the repetition is frequent in English its use in most cases is logically required and stylistically proved to be necessary. Otherwise, repetition is accepted as unnecessary component of the sentence or one of the stylistic shortcomings of the translation. The demand of syntactical completeness of the sentences and others stylistic criteria explain here the wide usage of *structure filling words*

(*almashtirladigan soʻzlar*). The structure filling words include pronouns (one, ones, this, that, these, those) and verbs (to do, to be, to have, shall, should, will, would, can, could, might, may, must, ought, need, dare).

Its quite evident that the structure filling words do not have denotative meaning, they are absolutely contextual. They should be related to conforming nouns and the verb form the fill and only afterwards they acquire lexical completeness. The verb-filling words are usually divided into two parts: fully filling and partially filling ones. To the first group belong the verb *to do* in the Present Indefinite which act in the role of fully filling word. It can replace the verbs of function. To the second group belong all other structure filling words. They act like a part of the whole just like the representative of compound verb form.

While translating the structure filling words we have to use words with complete meaning (sometimes pronouns) or make use of some other kinds of functional filling.

*The new British Government will face many problems, both acute and chronic: an acute **one** will be Northern Ireland, acute among chronic **ones** will be inflation and rising prices.*

Britaniyaning yangi hukumati shoshilinch va uzoq davom etadigan ko'plab muammolarga duch keladi. Shoshilinch masalalarga Shimoliy Irlandiyadagi vaziyat kiradi, uzoq davom etayotgan muammolarga esa inflyatsiya va narxlarning oshishi kiradi.

While translating this piece we had to decipher the structure filling words and render their meaning by means of conforming nouns.

When comparing the grammatical categories and forms of English and Uzbek languages we identify the following differences: a) the absence of the categories in one of the comparing languages, b) partial correspondence and c) complete correspondence. The necessity of grammatical transformations arise

only on two first cases. When comparing the English with Uzbek we should mention that Uzbek does not have the notions like article and gerund and absolute nominative constructions as well. Partial conformity and unconformity in meaning and usage of corresponding forms and constructions also demands grammatical transformations. We can refer to this case the partial unconformity of the category of number, partial unconformity in the forms of passive constructions, partial unconformity of the form of infinitive and gerund and some other differences in expressing the modality of the clause and so on.

In the following sentence both articles demands translation.

*The influence and authority of the UN Secretariat depends to **an** extent (though not nearly to **the** extent that is popularly supposed) on the talents of one individual – the Secretary-General. **The** job is a peculiar one.*

Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkiloti kotibiyatining ta'siri va vakolati ma'lum darajada (ko'pincha ishonilgan darajada bo'lmasa ham) bir shaxs - Bosh kotibning fazilatlariga bog'liq. Bu juda o'ziga xos pozitsiya.

The lexical meaning of the article is strongly expressed when it acts in like a link connecting parts of the sentences or two separate sentences as given in the example above. From the mentioned above cases we can judge that missing article translation may lead to misinterpretation or incorrect and incomplete translation of a sentence.

The role of verb complexes in English is quite evident therefore we will consider only some peculiar cases of verb transformations during translation.

Thus, all the considered cases – absence of conforming form, partial correspondence, differences in character and use – urge translators to make necessary grammatical transformations while translating some piece. Those grammatical transformations maybe divided into following types:

- 1) substitution
- 2) transposition

3) omission (ellipsis)

4) supplementation

Substitution is one of the grammatical relations among the parts of the sentences. In **substitution**, an item (or items) is replaced by another item (or items), ex:

I like politics.

And I do.

In this example, **do** is a substitute for **like politics**. Items commonly used in substitution in English include **do**, **one**, and **the same**, as in the following examples from Halliday and Hasan:

You think US will start the war against Iraq? – No one does.

We make use of substitution while translating a piece because of several reasons: absence of similar construction in Uzbek language, unconformity in usage of corresponding forms and constructions and some lexical reasons, which include different word usage and different norms of combinability in English and Uzbek and the absence of the part of speech with corresponding meaning.

An attempted overthrow in Peru.

*Peruda davlat to'ntarishiga **urinish**.*

In Uzbek we do not have the conforming participle II of the verb *пытаться*. And this made us change the part of speech; the participle **attempted** was translated into Uzbek by the noun **urinish**. The expression *davlat to'ntarishiga **urinish*** does conform to the norms of Uzbek language.

While translating the following text we will have to use substitution several times.

*On the whole the «popular» press – with the New York Daily News as its cheer-leader – **is vociferous in its support** of the President's policies and **merciless** toward those who attack them. But among the so-called «quality» papers led by the New York Times **there is a growing mood** of doubt and questioning.*

*Umuman olganda, “Nyu-York Daily News” boshchiligidagi “ommaviy” gazetalar prezident siyosatini **qattiq qo‘llab-quvvatlab**, ularni tanqid qilganlarga shafqatsizlarcha hujum qiladi. Ammo The New York Times boshchiligidagi “sifatli” gazetalar orasida shubha va noaniqlik **kayfiyati kuchaymoqda**.*

In the second sentence the introductory construction **there is** was translated by predicative verb and the participle **growing** was transformed into the function of an attribute. The noun **mood** was omitted and its attribute **of doubt and questioning** was turned into its object.

The transformation of ‘active’ into ‘passive’ is also when a translator uses substitution.

*More light **was shed** yesterday on the effect of C.S. gas, which **was claimed** by Pentagon to be virtually harmless to health.*

*Вчера **поступили дополнительные сведения** о вредном действии газа C.S., который, **по утверждению** Пентагона, якобы не опасен для здоровья.*

The phraseological unit **more light was shed** was translated by means of lexical transformation and the passive construction was replaced by an active one. The passive construction in the object clause also undergone lexical transformation – verbal construction was substituted by substantive one: **по утверждению**.

This example can illustrate the fact that lexical and grammatical transformations are closely related with each other.

It is very frequent when grammatical and lexical transformations demand supplementation or omission of some words or elements. Therefore omission and supplementation are frequently combined with other types of grammatical transformations and more frequently with substitution of parts of speech. Supplementation of parts of speech are characterized by several factors: difference in structures of the sentences and that short English sentences demand spread translation in the Uzbek language. Absence of some corresponding word

or lexical-semantic variant in both languages is also one of the reasons of applying additional words in translation.

*The American troops were **thought to be heading** toward Saigon, but no one seemed to be aware of fierce resistance of the nation.*

Amerika qo'shinlari Saygonga ketayotganiga ishonishdi, ammo mahalliy aholining qattiq qarshiliklari haqida hech kim bilmaganga o'xshaydi.

The construction Nominative + Infinitive with two omitted elements (*which was*) was given in object clause plus introductory sentences... *ketayotganga o'xshaydi...* . Thus, the difference in the structure of sentences demanded supplementation in the given translation.

In the following example, supplementation was caused by absence of corresponding word in Uzbek to English *conservationists*.

*The actions of Congress and of North Carolina and Tennessee statesmen, aided by gifts of wise **conservationists**, have set this land aside as Great Smoky National Park.*

Smoki-Hill daryosi qirg'og'idagi bu hudud Shimoliy Karolina va Tennessi shtatlari Kongressi va davlat arboblarning sa'y-harakatlari, shuningdek, tabiatni muhofaza qilish muhimligini tushunadigan tabiat shaydolarining xayr-ehsonlari tufayli Milliy bog'ga aylantirildi.

While translating this sentence besides transposition we have made many other transformations and as a matter of the first importance we should mention the supplementation we have accomplished. In regard to the absence of corresponding word in the Uzbek language to the English **conservationists** we have rendered it by two words **tabiat shaydolari**; and taking into consideration the combinability of the attribute **wise** we have translated it by adverbial modifier applying introductory words like **uni saqlash muhimligini tushunadiganlar**, the noun **saqlash** renders all the essence of the given sentence which is contained in **conservationists**.

So we can see that in the majority cases of translation some piece of political literature we have make necessary changes. We should remind you that it is not always an English sentence completely corresponds to the Uzbek one. Very frequently the structure of an Uzbek sentence absolutely differs from the one English. It has different word order, parts of the sentences and pretty often differs even the order of sentences. In some instances, parts of speech expressed in English are translated into Uzbek by the help of different parts of speech. You should remember that the compressed way of expression in the English can not be followed in Uzbek and we therefore have to «decompress» them so that to make the easy to perceive and understand, i.e. we have to add some words or expressions or even sentences in whole.

Nevertheless, some differences in usage of some specific features make us leave some elements unsaid while translating the whole. And all these cases are explained by grammatical transformations we have just investigated.

References

1. Abdelaal, N., & Abdelaal, N. (2020). Grammatical Problems in Translation. *Translation between English and Arabic: A Textbook for Translation Students and Educators*, 69-93.

2. Maksudovna, T. S., & Hikmatovna, K. S. (2017). Some grammatical problems of translation. *Достижения науки и образования*, (4 (17)), 42-43.